

BIOCONTROL POTENTIAL OF ENTOMOPATHOGENIC FUNGUS *BEAUVERIA BASSIANA* (BALSAMO) AGAINST *PERICALLIA RICINI* (FAB.) (LEPIDOPTERA: ARCTIIDAE) LARVAE

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ABSTRACT

In the recent study, the entomopathogenic fungus, *Beauveria bassiana* (Balsamo) used to evaluate its pathogenicity against *Pericallia ricini* Fab. (Lepidoptera: Arctiidae) third, fourth and fifth instars larvae. *B. bassiana* found effective at all concentrations i.e., 2×10^4 , 2×10^5 and 2×10^6 spores ml^{-1} on the *P. ricini*, but the uppermost concentration (2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1}) provided maximum control within short period of time ($P < 0.002$) than the other spore concentrations. Mortality of *P. ricini* was observed maximum on highest concentration of 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} . The value of LC_{50} lies between 2.32×10^2 and 13.89×10^7 spores ml^{-1} . *P. ricini* body weight was increased at 2.0×10^5 (452.7 ± 7.8 mg) spores ml^{-1} followed by 2.0×10^6 (450.9 ± 18.9) and 2.0×10^4 spores ml^{-1} (443.8 ± 6.2) by testing the field efficacy of *B. bassiana* against *P. ricini*, this insect pathogenic fungus can be used as potential biocontrol agent for the management of *P. ricini*. Results revealed that *B. bassiana* caused infection and caused death.

Key words : *Beauveria bassiana*, *Pericallia ricini*, insecticidal activity, biological control potential.

INTRODUCTION

Castor:

Castor, *Ricinus communis* (Linn.) is one of the most important cash crop cultivated in dry lands as monocrop or mixed crop with groundnut, chilly, cotton and cowpea, etc... One of the major problems with agriculture now-a-days is the demand for the production of more and more, in order to provide food for the population which is in permanent augmentation. In realizing this, one of the stumbling blocks seems to be the yield losses due to pests (Dubey *et al.*, 2008). There are fourteen insect pest affects the castor plant. Insect pests are mainly controlled with synthetic insecticides over the last 50 years

causing pesticide resistance and negative effects on non-target organisms, including humans, and also to the environment (Franzen, 1993). Hence alternative options like botanicals, natural enemies and microbial insecticides are subjected as well as practicing by farmers world-wide.

Pericallia ricini:

Pericallia ricini Fab. (Lepidoptera: Arctiidae) commonly called as hairy caterpillar or wooly bear is the major pest of castor, gingelly, cotton, country bean, brinjal, drum stick, coccina, banana, calotropis, sunflower, oleander, tea, sweat potato, pumpkin (David and Ananthkrishnan, 2004; Atluri *et al.*, 2010) and

vanilla (Vanitha *et al.*, 2011), radish (Asafali *et al.*, 1972), elephant foot, coccina, cow pea, yam, arum (Colocasia) (Nair, 1970; Butani and Jotwani, 1984; David, 2001).

Various mechanical, chemical (Tasida and Gobena, 2013) and botanical (Joseph *et al.*, 2010); mycoinsecticides (Sahayaraj and Borjio, 2012) pest control options have been used to control this pest. However, frequent misuse and abuse of chemical pesticides has led to the problems of pesticides resistance, resurgence and secondary out breaks of the pests besides several environmental hazards (Purwar and Sachan, 2006; Scholte *et al.*, 2006; Jaramillo and Borgemeister, 2006). Use the natural compounds in the place of conventional can reduce environmental pollution, preserve non-target organisms and avert insecticide, induced pest resurgence. In past years, neem oil has been used against *P. ricini* (Mala and Muthalagi, 2008). Whole-plant extracts of the perennial common herb, *Datura stramonium* L. showed insecticidal and antifeedant properties against *P. ricini* (Prakash and Rao, 1997).

Natural enemies:

Interest in the use of biopesticides with selectively against phytophagous insects has increased in recent years, particularly in cropping systems that rely on natural enemies as a major component of integrated pest management (Rausell *et al.*, 2000). *Mikania micrantha* Kundh (Mini Abraham *et al.*, 2002), *Vanilla planifolia* Andrews (vanitha *et al.*, 2011). braconid wasp, *Apanteles taragamae* were considered as natural enemies of *P. ricini* (Raja *et al.*, 2000).

Beauveria bassiana (Bals.) Vuillemin, is an entomopathogenic filamentous fungi plays an important role and have higher potential for biological control of sucking and defoliator insect pests (Butt *et al.*, 1994; Sahayaraj and Borgio, 2009, 2010). *Beauveria bassiana* is one of the most ubiquitous and extensively studied entomopathogenic fungi (Feng *et al.*, 1994; Hajek and St.Leger, 1994; Reithinger *et al.*, 1997; Arcas *et al.*, 1999; Meyling and Eilenberg, 2006; Freed *et al.*, 2011a, 2011b). It is a

deuteromycetaes fungus in the Moniliales and Moniliaece and is widely distributed in nature. Entomo-pathogenic fungi provide an environmentally responsive substitute to chemical pesticides. They are natural, easy to formulate, less toxic to mammals or vertebrates (Bradley *et al.*, 1992; Feng *et al.*, 1994; Goettel *et al.*, 1997) or non-target organisms (Feng *et al.*, 1994) or no residual activity (Copping, 2004) or less chance to develop resistance (Zimmermann, 2007).

Entomopathogenic fungi attack insects, important agents for biocontrol and a part of integrated pest management (Cooke, 1977). Quesada-Moraga *et al.* (2006) reported that some proteins extracted from *B. bassiana* isolates gave significant mortalities against *Spodoptera litura*.

Even though *B. bassiana* has been used to control various pests, none of the researchers used this fungus against the lepidopteran hairy caterpillars. Which causing very severe damage to most of the cash crops cultivated in world-wide. Very recently, Sahayaraj and Borgio (2010) evaluated the impact of *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Metsch). Sorokin (Deuteromycotina: Hyphomycetes) against this pest. With this background we have selected this *b. bassiana* for this present investigation to find their biological control efficacy against *P. ricini* under laboratory condition.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection and Rearing of Experimental animal:

Life stages of *P. ricini*, were collected from castor and cotton agroecosystems of Kottaiyur (N 9° 87' 33.9'', E 78° 66' 98.7''), Sivagangai District, Tamil Nadu, India. *Pericallia ricini* life stages were maintained on castor leaves at room temperature (29±2°C), relative humidity (70-80 %) and photoperiod of 11L and 13D Hrs in 1L capacity plastic containers (height 7.0 cm X diameter 15.0 cm). Laboratory emerged *P. ricini* adults (>1 day) separately were introduced into the oviposition chamber (height 43.7 cm X diameter 35.0 cm) and fed with 10% sucrose

solution fortified with a few drops of vitamin mixture (Supradyn Multi vitamin tablet) to enhance the oviposition. The egg batches were removed and kept in Petri dishes (height 1.5 cm X diameter 9.5 cm) for hatching. Laboratory reared 6-12 hrs prestarved third, fourth and fifth instar larvae were used for the experiment.

Fungal Isolate and Culture:

Beauveria bassiana pure culture was obtained from Crop Protection Research Centre (CPRC) stock culture. Spores were aseptically collected from the sub-culture of the isolate that had been purified using Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) (HiMedia, India). Inoculated test tubes were maintained at 28°C in an incubator till sporulation and the slope cultures were then maintained at 4°C. More than 15 days old working culture has not been utilized in the present study. The fungal conidia were collected from 7 days old cultures (2.5×10^7 conidia/ml) was prepared and considered as stock. Three spore concentrations such as 2.0×10^4 , 2.0×10^5 and 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} were prepared from the stock and their concentrations were determined using an improved Neubauer Haemocytometer (Pohem, Mumbai, India). Water was used as control. A homogeneous conidial suspension was prepared in sterile distilled water by adding few drops of Teepol oil (0.05%) 50 μl used as surfactant.

Bioassay

***Beauveria bassiana* spore concentrations:**

At least 1ml (2.0×10^4 , 2.0×10^5 and 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1}) different concentrations were used of fungal conidial suspension was sprayed on third, fourth and fifth instar larvae by hand sprayer (Plastic Spray Bottle, Mumbai). After 10 minutes, fungal spore treated larvae were transferred and released into clean plastic containers (height 5.3 cm X diameter 4.0 cm) and provided with fresh and healthy castor leaves. The unfed leaves and fecal pellets of the insect was removed every 24 hrs still 96 hrs. The weight gain and mortality were recorded up to 96 hrs for each instars separately. In each contrasion 30 insects were used with six replications.

Statistical Analysis:

Finney's formula was used to calculate corrected mortality (Finney, 1971). From the corrected mortality data, the probability integral of the chi-square distribution, regression equation, slope and lethal concentrations (LC_{30} , LC_{50} and LC_{90}) were calculated in order to find out the efficacy of *B. bassiana* and SAULCA 3EC against life stages of the pest. The Probit analysis (Finney, 1971) was analyzed using SPSS 20 Version software.

RESULTS

The tested fungi against *P. ricini* showed pathogenecity at different conidial concentrations.

Mortality:

Even sized third, fourth and fifth instars larvae of *P. ricini* was objected to three different concentrations of *B. bassiana* showed concentration depended mortality (Table 1, 2 and 3). Three different conidial concentrations at 2.0×10^4 , 2.0×10^5 and 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} of *B. bassiana* caused 100% mortality on *P. ricini* larvae under laboratory conditions. The larval mortality was observed up to ninth day after the fungal spore exposure. Among the three spore concentrations of *B. bassiana*, 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} was more pathogenic ($\text{df}=3, 2$; $F=526.889$; $P<0.002$) than other spore concentrations. On eleventh day, 100% mortality was recorded by all tested concentrations of the fungus. All the cadavers of *P. ricini* showed sporulation of the fungus, indicating that death was caused by infection of the fungi under laboratory conditions.

At 2.0×10^4 spores ml^{-1} , during second day, both fourth instar ($\text{df}=1,4$; $F=0.167$; $P=0.704$) and fifth instar ($\text{df}=1,4$; $F=0.167$; $P=0.704$) showed same response (mortality). Similar mortality was recorded on the third day ($\text{df}=2,3$; $F=1.167$; $P=0.422$ and $\text{df}=2,3$; $F=1.00$; $P=0.465$ for fourth and fifth instar larvae respectively) and fourth day ($\text{df}=1,4$; $F=0.205$; $P=0.674$ and $\text{df}=1,4$; $F=0.205$; $P=0.674$ for fourth and fifth instar respectively). Similar mortality was also

recorded on the fifth day (df=2,3; F=0.208; P=0.823 and df=2,3; F=0.150; P=0.867 for fourth and fifth instar larvae respectively) and (df=3,2; F=1.555; P=0.414 and df=3,2; F=1.155; P=0.495 for third and fourth instar larvae respectively). On eighth day, higher mortality was recorded in the fifth instar (df=2,3; F=6.377; P<0.083).

Table 1. Impact of *B. bassiana* at 2×10^4 spores ml^{-1} on the corrected mortality of *P. ricini* third, fourth and fifth instars larvae during 10 days observation (n=21; Mean±SE)

Day(s)	Larval stage(s)		
	Third instars	Fourth instars	Fifth instars
1	5.7±0.5	5.6±0.7	11.1±0.7
2	5.7±0.6	11.1±0.1	12.2±0.8
3	11.1±0.7	16.7±0.6	22.2±0.1
4	11.1±0.7	22.2±0.1	33.3±0.4
5	22.2±1.1	27.8±0.1	44.4±1.2
6	38.9±0.5	49.9±1.1	55.6±1.1
7	44.4±0.7	55.6±1.1	61.1±1.02
8	55.6±1.1	66.7±0.8	8.3±1.1
9	100.0±0.0	88.9±0.7	88.9±0.7
10	100.0±0.0	100.0±0.0	100.0±0.0

Table 2. Impact of *B. bassiana* at 2×10^5 spores ml^{-1} on the corrected mortality of *P. ricini* third, fourth and fifth instars larvae during 11 days observation (n=21; Mean±SE)

Day(s)	Larval stage(s)		
	Third instars	Fourth instars	Fifth instars
1	0.0±0.0	11.1±0.1	0.0±0.0
2	0.0±0.0	16.7±0.2	11.1±1.1
3	0.0±0.0	27.3±0.3	16.7±0.2
4	5.6±0.1	33.3±0.4	38.9±0.5
5	16.7±0.2	50.0±0.7	44.4±1.10
6	27.8±0.3	55.6±1.1	55.6±1.1
7	38.9±0.5	61.1±1.1	66.7±0.8
8	55.6±0.7	77.8±0.8	83.3±0.7
9	66.7±0.6	88.9±0.7	83.3±0.7
10	77.8±0.7	100.0±0.0	100.0±0.0
11	100.0±0.0	100.0±0.0	100.0±0.0

At 2.0×10^5 spores ml^{-1} , on third day, more mortality was recorded in the fifth instar (df=2,3; F8.996; P,0.054). During fifth day, both third (df=1,4; F=1.000; P=0.374) and fourth (df=1,4; F=1.000; P=0.374) instar larvae showed same

response (mortality). On the sixth day, more mortality was recorded in the fifth instar larvae (df=1,4; F=7.108; P<0.056). Similar response was showed by both third (df=2,3; F=0.375; P=0.716) and fifth instar (df=2,3; F=0.375; P=0.715) larvae on the sixth day. During seventh day, more mortality was recorded in the fifth instar (df=1,4; F=6.003; P<0.070). On ninth day, third and fifth instar larvae (df=1,4; F=0.000; P=1.000 and df=1,4; F=0.000; P=1.000) and also fourth instar (df=1,4; F=0.000; P=1.000) showed same response.

Table 3. Impact of *B. bassiana* at 2×10^6 spores ml^{-1} on the corrected mortality of *P. ricini* third, fourth and fifth instars larvae during 10 days observation (n=21; Mean±SE)

Day(s)	Larval stage(s)		
	Third instars	Fourth instars	Fifth instars
1	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	5.6±0.5
2	0.0±0.0	5.7±0.1	22.2±0.7
3	0.0±0.0	11.1±0.5	27.8±0.8
4	5.6±0.5	16.6±0.5	27.8±0.8
5	22.2±0.7	22.2±0.7	38.9±0.4
6	33.3±0.8	44.4±0.9	55.6±1.1
7	50.0±0.7	49.9±1.1	66.7±0.8
8	55.6±0.7	77.8±1.1	83.3±0.7
9	72.2±1.1	83.3±1.1	83.3±0.7
10	100.0±0.0	100.0±0.0	100.0±0.0

At 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} , during second day, more mortality was recorded in the fifth instar (df=1,4; F=32.674; P<0.005). Similar response was showed by third (df=2,3; F=0.682; P=0.570) and fifth instar (df=2,3; F=0.750; P=0.544) larvae on seventh day. Though the tested larvae feed the castor leaves voraciously for the first two days, they slowly decreased their feeding response which leads to starvation and finally the insects died.

LC₅₀

At 96 hrs, the LC₅₀ analysis shows that the mortality of third instar larvae (LC₅₀= 7.7) was more when compared to fourth instar larvae (LC₅₀= 2.3) and fifth instar larvae (LC₅₀=13.895) (Table 4). Previously it was reported that the *B. bassiana* has the potential to control over 70 insects pest of various crops and appears to be

Table 4. Impact of *B. bassiana* 2×10^4 , 2×10^5 and 2×10^6 spores ml^{-1} on probit analysis data for *P. ricini* third, fourth and fifth instars larvae

Larval stage	LC ₃₀	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	Significance	Chi-square	Slope	Regression equation
Third	1.5	7.71	41.32	0.160	1.976	0.72	Y=-249.567+2.8X
Fourth	1.26	2.32	10.19	0.378	0.777	1.84	Y=-508.65+5.55X
Fifth	8.26	13.89	49.58	0.164	1.934	1.87	Y=-509.833+5.0X

innocuous to most non- target organisms (Feng *et al.*, 1994). Purwar and Sachan (2005) reported that in general, *B. bassiana* was more virulent than *M. anisopliae* to *Spodoptera* spp. Results reveals the effectiveness of *B. bassiana* against different stages of *P. ricini*. The fungi causing the pathogenecity in insects have been observed to cause mortality in insect population and therefore studied for their use as biological control agents It is economically important to determine the optimal concentration of conidia for spray applications to reduce the overall cost of pest control while achieving high control efficiency. The LC₅₀ value reveals that *B. bassiana* virulence potential is different for different life stages of the same pest, *P. ricini* (Table 4).

Larval weight:

After 96 hrs of exposure, *P. ricini* third, fourth and fifth instars body weight was increased. In third instar larva, the weight was increased to 452.7 ± 7.8 mg at 2.0×10^5 (df=4,1; F=60.354; P<0.042) spores ml^{-1} , followed by 2.0×10^6 (df=3,2; F=28.886; P<0.034) spores ml^{-1} (450.9 ± 18.9 mg) and 2.0×10^4 (df=4,1; F=75.167; P<0.086) spores ml^{-1} (443.8 ± 16.2 mg) (Figure 2). In fourth instar larval weight was increased at 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} (497.4 ± 30.9 mg) followed by 2.0×10^4 (443.8 ± 59.3 mg) and 2.0×10^5 spores ml^{-1} (441.6 ± 40.3 mg) (Figure 3). In fifth instar larvae weight was increased at 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} (606.4 ± 80.7 mg) (Figure 4) followed by 2.0×10^4 (602.2 ± 40.5 mg) and 2.0×10^5 (523.9 ± 48.7 mg) spores ml^{-1} .

Thrid instar:

2.0×10^4 , 2.0×10^5 and 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} were significant. In third instar larvae, the weight was increased significantly at 2.0×10^5 spores ml^{-1} . The comparison between 2.0×10^4 at 0 hrs and 2.0×10^4 at 48 hrs (df=4,1; F=79.194; P<0.084)

and 2.0×10^4 at 0 hours and 2.0×10^4 at 96 hrs (df=4,1; F=79.194; P<0.065) were significant. Similarly comparison between 2.0×10^6 at 0 hrs and 2.0×10^6 at 24 hrs (df=3,2; F=20.256; P<0.04). 2.0×10^6 at 0 hrs with 2.0×10^6 at 48 hrs (df=3,2; F= 526.889; P<0.002). 2.0×10^6 0 hrs with 2.0×10^6 at 72 hrs (df=3,2; F=28.446; P<0.034) were significant. Further the comparison between 2.0×10^4 at 0 hrs to 2.0×10^6 at 0 hrs (df=4,1; F=156.500; P<0.060); 2.0×10^6 at 0 hrs with 2.0×10^5 during the same period (df=3,2; F=23.164; P<0.042); 2.0×10^4 at 48 hrs to 2.0×10^5 at 48 hrs (df=4,1; F=60.354; P<0.096); 2.0×10^5 at 48 hrs to 2.0×10^4 at 48 hrs (df=4,1; F=79.194; P<0.084) were statistically significant.

Fourth instar:

In fourth instar larvae, the weight was increased at 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} , was significantly increased at 2.0×10^4 0 hrs then when compared with 2.0×10^4 at 96 hrs (df=4,1; F=1161.114; P<0.059). Same trend was also observed between 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} at 24 hrs and 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} at 72 hrs (df=4,1; F=5375.750; P<0.010) were significant.

Fifth instar:

In fifth instar, the larval weight was increased significantly when comparison was made between 2.0×10^5 spores ml^{-1} at 24 hrs compared with 2.0×10^5 at 72 hrs (df=4, 1; F=819.602; P<0.026) and also between 2.0×10^5 at 24 hrs 2.0×10^5 in control (df=3,1; F=6391.133; P<0.009).

The extensive control efficacy of *B. bassiana* against grasshoppers (Hazarika and Puzari, 1997), colorado potato beetle, Japanese beetle, Mexican been beetle and Japanese beetle (Wagner and Lewis, 2000) white flies (Wraight *et al.*, 2000), boll weevil (Sandhu *et al.*, 2001),

Figure 1. Impact of *Beauveria bassiana* (2×10^4 spores ml^{-1}) on weight gain (mg) of *Pericallia ricini* third (a), fourth (b) and fifth (c) instars larvae during 24, 48, 72 and 96 hrs of exposure

Figure 2. Impact of *Beauveria bassiana* (2×10^5 spores ml^{-1}) on weight gain (mg) of *Pericallia ricini* third (a), fourth (b) and fifth (c) instars larvae during 24, 48, 72 and 96 hrs of exposure

Figure 3. Impact of *Beauveria bassiana*(2×10^6 spores ml^{-1}) on weight gain (mg) of *Pericallia ricini* third (a), fourth (b) and fifth (c) instars larvae during 24, 48, 72 and 96hrs of exposure

chinch bug (Castrillo *et al.*, 2003), fire ants, lepidopteran caterpillars (Moorthi *et al.*, 2011), aphides (Akmal *et al.*, 2013) and termite *Macrotermes michealseni* (Mburu *et al.*, 2013) and have been available in the literature.

From our results it is concluded that *B. bassiana* is effective at all concentrations of 2.0×10^4 , 2.0×10^5 and 2.0×10^6 spores ml^{-1} on the *P. ricini* can give maximum control within short period of time. The use of biopesticides including entomopathogenic fungi is generally perceived to be ecologically preferable for pest control (Panda *et al.*, 2014), Purwar and Sachan, 2006; Scholte *et al.*, 2006; Jaramillo and Borgemeister, 2006).

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